

The Chatterjea fixed point theorem on CCRM - spaces

K. Prudhvi *

Department of Mathematics, University College of Science, Saifabad,
Osmania University, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

Received: 17 Feb 2026

Accepted: 04 May 2026

Published Online: 30 May 2026

Abstract: In the present paper, we obtain a fixed point result on CCRM (Complete Cone Rectangular) - Spaces. We extend the results of Jleli and samet results existing in the literature.

Key words: Cone metric space, cone rectangular metric space, fixed point, normal cone.

AMS subject classifications: 47H10, 54H25.

1. Introduction and Preliminaries

Banach fixed point theorem is first and foremost one in fixed point theory and lot of generalizations has been done in this theorem. Huang and Zhang [5] have introduced the concept of cone metric space, where the set of real numbers is replaced by an ordered Banach space and they obtained fixed point results for contractive type conditions in normal cone metric space. Subsequently many authors has been studying and generalizing this cone metric space [see for e.g.[1-8], [9-16]. Branciari [3], Azam, Arshad and Beg [1] extended the notion of cone metric spaces by replacing the triangular inequality by a rectangular inequality. Recently. Jleli and Samet [4] obtained a fixed point theorem in a cone rectangular metric space. In this paper, we have generalized and extended the results of [4].

We need some of preliminary definitions in our main result which are due to [4].

Definition 1.1. Let M always be a real Banach space and P a subset of M . Q is called a cone if and only if:

- (a). Q is closed, non empty, and $Q \neq 0$.
- (b). $\alpha, \beta \in R, \alpha, \beta \geq 0, x, y \in Q$ implies $\alpha x + \beta y \in Q$.
- (c). $x \in Q$ and $-x \in Q$ implies $x = 0$.

Definition 1.2. Given a cone $Q \subset M$, we define a partial ordering \leq with respect to Q by : $x \leq y$ iff $y - x \in Q$. We shall write $x < y$ to indicate that $x \leq y$ but $x \neq y$, while $x \ll y$ will stand for $y - x \in$ interior of Q .

Definition 1.3. The cone Q is called normal if there is a number $L > 0$ such that for all $x, y \in M, 0 \leq x \leq y$ implies $\|x\| \leq L\|y\|$ where $\|\cdot\|$ is the norm in M . In this case the number L is called the normal constant of Q .

In the following we always suppose M is a Banach space, Q is a cone in M with $\text{int } Q \neq \phi$ and \leq is partial ordering with respect to Q .

©Asia Matematika, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20982726](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20982726)

*Correspondence: prudhvikasani@rocketmail.com

Definition 1.4. Let X be a non- empty set. Suppose the $\rho : X \rightarrow X$ satisfies the following:

- (a). $\rho(x, y) > 0$ for all $x, y \in X$ and $\rho(x, y) = 0$ if and only if $x = y$.
- (b). $\rho(x, y) = \rho(y, x)$, for all $x, y \in X$.
- (c). $\rho(x, y) \leq \rho(x, w) + \rho(w, z) + \rho(z, y)$, for all $x, y \in X$ and for all distinct points $w, z \in X - x, y$ [rectangular property]. Then ρ is called a cone rectangular metric on X , and (X, ρ) is called a cone rectangular metric space.

Definition 1.5. Let (X, ρ) be a cone rectangular metric space. Let (x_n) be a sequence in X and $x \in X$. If for every $d \in M$, $d \gg 0$ there is N such that for all $n > N$, $\rho(x_n, x) \ll d$, then (x_n) is said to be convergent to x and x is the limit of (x_n) . We denote this $x_n \rightarrow x$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Definition 1.6. Let (X, ρ) be a cone rectangular metric space. Let (x_n) be a sequence in X and $x \in X$. If for every $d \in M$, $d \gg 0$ there is N such that for all $n, m > N$, $\rho(x_n, x_m) \ll d$, then (x_n) is said to be Cauchy sequence in X .

Definition 1.7. Let (X, ρ) be a cone rectangular metric space. If every Cauchy sequence is convergent, then X is called a CCRM(Complete Cone Rectangular Metric)-space.

Lemma 1.1. Let (X, ρ) be a cone rectangular metric space and M be a normal cone. Let (x_n) be a sequence in X . Then (x_n) Cauchy sequence in X if and only if, $\rho(x_n, x_m) \rightarrow 0$ as $m, n \rightarrow \infty$.

2. Main Result

Theorem 2.1. Let (N, ρ) be a CCRM-Space, S be a normal cone with normal constant L . Suppose a mapping $A : N \rightarrow N$ satisfies the following contraction condition

$$\rho(Ax, Ay) \leq a[\rho(x, Ay) + \rho(y, Ax)]. \quad (1)$$

For all $x, y \in X$, where $a \in [0, 1/2)$. Then

- (i). A has a fixed point in X .
- (ii). for any $x \in X$ the iterative sequence $\{A^n x\}$ converges to the fixed point.

Proof. Let $x \in N$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(Ax, A^2x) &\leq a[\rho(x, A^2x) + \rho(Ax, Ax)], \\ &\leq a\rho(x, A^2x), \\ &\leq a[\rho(x, Ax) + \rho(Ax, A^2x)], \\ &\leq \frac{a}{1-a}\rho(x, Ax). \end{aligned}$$

Again

$$\begin{aligned}
 \rho(A^2x, A^3x) &\leq a[\rho(Ax, A^3x) + \rho(A^2x, A^2x)], \\
 &\leq a\rho(Ax, A^3x), \\
 &\leq a[\rho(Ax, A^x) + \rho(A^2x, A^3x)], \\
 &\leq \frac{a}{1-a}\rho(Ax, A^2x). \\
 &\leq \left[\frac{a}{1-a}\right]^2\rho(Ax, x).
 \end{aligned}$$

Then in general n is positive integer,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \rho(A^2x, A^3x) &\leq \left[\frac{a}{1-a}\right]^n\rho(Ax, x). \\
 &\leq h^n\rho(Ax, x), \text{ where } h = \frac{a}{1-a} \in [0, 1).
 \end{aligned}$$

We divide the proof into two cases:

Case-i: Let $A^m x = A^n x$ for some $m, n \in \mathbb{N}, m \neq n$. Let $m > n$, then

$$A^{m-n}(A^n x) = A^n x, \text{ that is, } A^p y = y, \text{ where } p = m - n, y = A^n x.$$

Now since $p > 1$ we have

$$\rho(y, Ay) = \rho(A^p x, A^{p+1} x) \leq h^p \rho(y, Ay).$$

Since $h \in [0, 1)$, we obtain

$$-\rho(y, Ay) \in P \text{ and } \rho(y, Ay) \in P.$$

Implies that $\|\rho(y, Ay)\| = 0$. That is, $y = Ay$.

Case-ii: Assume that $A^m x \neq A^n x$ for some $m, n \in N, m \neq n$. Let $m > n$, clearly we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \rho(A^n x, A^{n+1} x) &\leq h^p \rho(x, Ax) \\
 &\leq \frac{h^n}{1-h} \rho(x, Ax),
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 \rho(A^n x, A^{n+2} x) &\leq a[\rho(A^{n-1} x, A^{n+2} x) + \rho(A^{n+1} x, A^n x)], \\
 &= a[\rho(A^{n-1} x, A^n x) + \rho(A^{n+1} x, A^n x)], \\
 &= a[\rho(A^{n-1} x, A^n x) + \rho(A^n x, A^{n+2} x) + \rho(A^{n+1} x, A^n x)], \\
 &= a[h^n \rho(x, Ax) + \rho(A^n x, A^{n+1} x) + \rho(A^{n+1} x, A^{n+2} x) + h^n \rho(Ax, x)],
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= a[h^{n-1}\rho(Ax, x) + h^n\rho(Ax, x) + h^{n+1}\rho(Ax, x) + h^n\rho(Ax, x)], \\
&\leq a[h^{n-1}\rho(Ax, x) + 2h^n\rho(Ax, x) + h^{n+1}\rho(Ax, x)], \\
&\leq h^n\rho(Ax, x) + 2h^n\rho(Ax, x) + h^{n+1}\rho(Ax, x), \\
&\leq 3h^n\rho(Ax, x) + h^{n+1}\rho(Ax, x), \\
&\leq \frac{h^n}{1-h}\rho(x, Ax).
\end{aligned}$$

If $m > 2$ is odd then write $m = 2l + 1$, $l > 1$ and using the fact that $A^p x \neq A^h x$ for $p, h \in N$, $p \neq h$, we can easily show that

$$\begin{aligned}
\rho(A^n x, A^{n+m} x) &\leq \rho(A^n x, A^{n+1} x) + \rho(A^{n+1} x, A^n x) + \rho(A^{n+1} x, A^{n+2} x) + \dots + \rho(A^{n+2l} x, A^{n+2l+1} x), \\
&\leq h^n \rho(x, Ax) + h^{n+1} \rho(x, Ax) + \dots + h^{n+2l} \rho(x, Ax), \\
&\leq h^n [1 + h + h^2 + \dots] \rho(x, Ax), \\
&\leq \frac{h^n}{1-h} \rho(x, Ax).
\end{aligned}$$

Again if $m > 2$ is even then written as $m = 2l$, $l \geq 2$ and using the same arguments as before we get that

$$\begin{aligned}
\rho(A^n x, A^{n+m} x) &\leq \rho(A^n x, A^{n+2} x) + \rho(A^{n+2} x, A^{n+3} x) + \dots + \rho(A^{n+2l-1} x, A^{n+2l} x), \\
&\leq h^n \rho(x, Ax) + h^{n+2} \rho(x, Ax) + \dots + h^{n+2l} \rho(x, Ax), \\
&\leq h^n [1 + h + h^2 + \dots] \rho(x, Ax), \\
&\leq \frac{h^n}{1-h} \rho(x, Ax).
\end{aligned}$$

Then combining all the above cases we have

$$\rho(A^n x, A^{n+m} x) \leq \frac{h^n}{1-h} \rho(x, Ax) \text{ for all } m, n \in N.$$

Hence we get that

$$\|\rho(A^n x, A^{n+m} x)\| \leq K \frac{h^n}{1-h} \|\rho(x, Ax)\| \text{ for all } m, n \in N.$$

Since

$$K \frac{h^n}{1-h} \|\rho(x, Ax)\| \longrightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \longrightarrow \infty$$

Claim: $Ax^* = x^*$. Without loss of generality we assume that $Ax^* \neq x^*$, for any $n \in N$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\rho(x^*, Ax^*) &\leq \rho(x^*, A^n x) + \rho(A^n x, A^{n+1} x) + \rho(A^{n+1} x, Ax^*), \\
&\leq \rho(x^*, A^n x) + \rho(A^n x, A^{n+1} x) + \rho(A^{n+1} x, Ax^*), \\
&\leq \rho(x^*, A^n x) + \rho(A^n x, A^{n+1} x) + a[\rho(A^n x, Ax^*) + \rho(x^*, A^{n+1} x^*)]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\rho(x^*, Ax^*) \leq 0.$$

Therefore, $\rho(x^*, Ax^*) = 0$.

That implies $x^* = Ax^*$. Therefore A has a fixed point. □

Conclusion

In this paper, our results are extended and generalized results of [4].

Acknowledgment

The author thankful to the reviewers to review this article and give the valuable suggestions for improvement and in the present form.

References

- [1] A. Azam, M. Arshad and I.Beg, banach contraction principle on cone rectangular metric spaces, *Applicable Analysis and Discrete mathematics*, 3(2009), 236-241.
- [2] A. Azam and M. Arshad, Kannan fixed point theorem on generalized metric spaces, *The J. Nonlinear. Sci.*, 1(2008),no.1,45-48.
- [3] A. Branciari, A fixed point theorem of Banach-Caccippoli type on a class of generalized metric spaces, *Publ. Math. Debrecen*, 57/1-2 (2000), 31-37.
- [4] M. Jleli and B. Samet, The Kannan's fixed point theorem in a cone rectangular metric space, *Nonlinear Sci. Appl.* 2(2009), no.3, 161-167.
- [5] L.G.Huang, X.Zhang, Cone metric spaces and fixed point theorems of contractive mappings, *J. Math. Anal. Appl.* 332(2)(2007)1468-1476.
- [6] R. Kannan, Some results on fixed points, *Bull. Calcutta math.Soc.*,60(1968), 71-76.
- [7] S. Moradi, Kannan fixed point theorem on complete metric spaces and on generalized metric spaces depended an another function, *arXiv:0903.1577 v1[math; FA]*,9 Mar(2009),1-6.
- [8] K.Prudhvi, Study on "Fixed Point Results" for Pair of Maps in CMS, *Asian Basic and Applied Research Journal*, Volume 5, Issue 1, (2023), 129-131.
- [9] K. Prudhvi, A unique common fixed point theorem in cone metric spaces, *Advances in Fixed Point Theory*, 3(2013), No.1,70-76.
- [10] K. Prudhvi, Study on Fixed Points for OWC in Symmetric Spaces, *Asia Mathematika*, Vol.7, Issue 3, (2023), 72-75.
- [11] K. Prudhvi, Common fixed points on occasionally weakly compatible self- mappings in CMS, *Asia Mathematika*,Vol.7, Issue.2, (2023), 13-16.
- [12] K. Prudhvi, Results on fixed points for WC-Mappings satisfying generalized contractive condition in C- metric spaces, *Asia Mathematika*, Vol. 8 Issue 1, (2024), 112 – 117.
- [13] K. Prudhvi, A unique common fixed point result for compatible reciprocal continuous four self - maps in complete metric space, *Asia Mathematika*, Vol. 8 Issue: 3, (2024), 10 – 13.
- [14] K.Prudhvi, Study on Extended B-K Fixed Point Theorem on CGM-Space Depended on an Another Function *Asia Mathematika* Vol.5, Issue 2, (2025), 25-28.
- [15] K.Prudhvi, A Unique Fixed Point Result on C-G-MS, *Asia Mathematika*,Vol.9, Issue2, (2025), 47-50.
- [16] B.E.Rhoades, A comparison of various definitions of contractive mappings, *Trans. Amer. Math. Sci.* 26(1977), 257-290.